

CHARACTERIZING THERMO-OXIDATIVE BEHAVIOR OF MULTI-DIRECTIONAL LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

In this work, the influence of ply stacking sequence on oxidation growth is investigated in isothermally aged multi-directional composites through the use of fluorescence imaging using dye impregnation in conjunction with optical microscopy. Oxidation simulations are performed for some selected laminates and the resulting trends are correlated with experimental observations.

Keywords: Thermo-oxidation, Aging, Microscopy, Micromechanics, Damage

INTRODUCTION

The anisotropy of oxidation of polymer matrix composites was first documented by Nelson [1] when he observed that the oxidation process was sensitive to the surface area for the different test specimens that he aged. Subsequently, numerous other investigators (e.g., Bowles, et al. [2], Nam and Seferis [3], Schoeppner, et al. [4], and Tandon, et al. [5]) have also observed the anisotropic nature of oxidation in high-temperature unidirectional polymer matrix composites. In unidirectional composites, the diffusion limited oxidation behavior of polymer matrix composites is predominantly controlled by the properties of the resin and the fiber-matrix interface and the total surface area through which the oxygen can diffuse. Various factors may lead [6] to the preferential oxidation along the fiber paths. Resin cure shrinkage and mismatches in the coefficient of thermal expansion of the fibers and matrix during the composite cure process give rise to localized micromechanical residual stresses in the fiber-matrix interphase region. The diffusion process in materials has been shown [7] to increase with increasing stress levels even becoming nonlinear, as a function of stress, for

materials with linear mechanical behavior. Another factor that may lead to preferential oxidation along the fiber is that the local stoichiometry of the polymer may be altered in the fiber-matrix interphase region by the presence of glass fiber-reinforced coupling agents or graphite fiber-reinforced sizing agents. The presence of the sizing can have a strong influence on the fiber-matrix interphase or interfacial properties and can ultimately affect the local diffusivity and/or thermal oxidative stability. In addition, severe surface oxidation degradation results in the formation of transverse surface cracks coalescing with fiber-matrix disbands. These cracks not only reduce strength, but also create enhanced pathways for oxygen to penetrate deeper into the composite.

In laminated systems, interlaminar residual stresses (besides the fiber-matrix micromechanical stresses at the ply level), further play an important role in the degradation process. In a study by Bowles, et al. [8], both unidirectional and cross-ply (± 45) PMR-15 laminates were isothermally aged at 288°C for up to 1,000 hours. They found that the weight loss of the cross-ply laminates was much greater than that of the unidirectional laminates. The primary reason given for the greater weight loss in the cross-ply laminates was that free-edge cracks, resulting from interlaminar residual stresses, in the cross-ply laminates were much more prominent and resulted in more extensive advancement of oxidation into the interior of the composite. Similar observations were made by Tsotsis and Lee [9] who examined the long-term thermo-oxidative degradation behavior of G30-500/R922-1 and G30-500/R6376 carbon-fiber reinforced epoxy composites. Their results indicated that residual stresses arising from aging-induced differential resin shrinkage and interaction between plies of different orientations were found to have a strong effect on the degradation process for plies close to the surface and, especially, near free edges. Recently, Rouquie, et al [10] performed thermal cycling tests on three different carbon/epoxy laminates: $[0_3/90_3]_S$, $[45_3/-45_3]_S$ and $[45/0/-45/90]_S$ in nitrogen and air. Microscopic observations and X-radiographs showed an acceleration of matrix cracking and matrix shrinkage due to coupling between oxidation and cyclic thermal stresses. Moreover, damage observations on the polished edges of the samples were highly dependant on the laminate stacking sequence.

In this work, the influence of ply stacking sequence on oxidation growth is investigated. Light microscopy techniques are used to characterize the oxidative process in laminated carbon fiber-reinforced polyimide composites. Four different laminates are considered, namely, $[0]_{16T}$, $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$, $[0/90]_{4S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$. Isothermal aging was conducted at 177°C. Oxidation-induced damage development was examined through fluorescence imaging using dye impregnation in conjunction with optical microscopy techniques. A hierarchical modeling methodology is used to simulate observed oxidation growth patterns in laminated composites. The methodology entails modeling oxidation and damage growth mechanisms at the neat-resin, lamina and laminate scales. The oxidative degradation and damage growth in the polymeric resin are determined using a coupled model [11] that tracks oxygen diffusion, oxidation reaction and mechanical behavior changes in the resin. The resin and fiber behavior models are then utilized in a representative volume element (RVE) to determine the oxidation characteristics at the lamina scale. Lamina-scale RVE analyses together with homogenization techniques are used to determine diffusion, reaction and damage growth parameters to be used at the laminate scale. Oxidation simulations are performed for some selected lamina stacking sequences and the resulting trends are correlated with experimental observations.

TESTING AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Two rectangular specimens measuring approximately 125 mm × 12.5 mm × 2.3 mm were used to monitor oxidation propagation and damage development along the length and transverse to the fibers. The isothermal aging was accomplished in an air-circulating oven that provided a continuous replenishment of oxygen in the ambient air by convection through the oven inlet. At specified sparse time intervals, specimens were removed from the ovens and samples were dry-sectioned from the aged larger specimen, potted in epoxy and polished as illustrated in Figure 1. This allowed monitoring of four of the exposed edges of the large specimen. The large sample was subsequently placed back in the oven to continue the aging process. Additional details on specimen handling, aging and vacuum impregnation procedure are included in [5].

Figure 1: Oxidation measurement procedures

Dark-field microscopy was utilized to monitor the oxidation propagation in $[0]_{16T}$, $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$, $[0/90]_{4S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminates. The oxidation layer formation near the exposed specimen edges changes the optical characteristics of the material, and the oxidized layer is observed by light microscopy. Specifically, the oxidation layer appears as a frame around the composite cross-section, and is clearly seen as the lighter oxidized material using standard light microscopy in the grayscale mode. Figure 2 shows the extent of oxidation near the laminate edges in a cross-section parallel to 0° direction in a $[0]_{16T}$ composite, as a function of aging time. Note that each observation of extent of oxidation is for a unique cross section of the sample since the specimen preparation process, which includes sectioning, impregnating, and polishing specimens at each discrete aging time, precludes tracking oxidation growth on a unique cross-section.

Figure 2: Oxidation growth near the laminate edge in a cross-section parallel to 0° direction in $[0]_{16T}$ laminate as a function of aging time

It is clearly evident that with increase of aging time, the axial propagation of the oxidation is much greater than the oxidation in the transverse direction. Also, with aging time, the front of the axial oxidation becomes non-uniform through the thickness, and can clearly be seen following the fiber paths and is dominating the oxidation process. On the other hand, small changes are observed in the oxidation thickness in the transverse direction with aging time. Figure 3 shows the extent of oxidation near the laminate edges in a cross-section perpendicular to 0° direction in a $[0]_{16T}$ composite. In this cross section orientation, the oxidized region appears as a picture frame near the exposed free surfaces of the specimen, and the behavior is similar to that of the neat resin. Moreover, the oxidation thickness is fairly uniform around the entire cross section, and shows only marginal growth, for the aging times considered.

Figure 3: Oxidation growth near the laminate edge in a cross-section perpendicular to 0° direction in $[0]_{16T}$ laminate as a function of aging time

Figure 4 shows the oxidation growth with aging time in a *cross-section perpendicular to 0° direction* in $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate. Unlike the relatively uniform oxidation front observed for the unidirectional laminate, we observe preferential oxidation growth along the fiber paths for the cross-ply laminate. Moreover, oxidation is no longer uniform through the ply thickness even at short aging times, as individual plies influence neighboring plies in a multi-directional laminate. The oxidation propagation rate in a ply is strongly influenced by the orientation of its neighboring plies. For example, a 0° ply will tend to increase the oxidation rate in a neighboring off-axis ply as compared to its oxidation rate in a unidirectional composite of the same off-axis orientation. Similarly a 90° ply will tend to decrease the oxidation rate in neighboring plies of different orientation. For the $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate, the maximum and minimum oxidation extents with individual plies occurs at their midplane due to the fact that the adjacent top and bottom plies in the interior of the laminate are symmetric about the midplane of a ply of interest. As seen in Figure 4, this non-uniform oxidation front advances and the non-uniformity becomes more pronounced because of the differences in oxidation growth rates for the two ply orientations. On the other hand, the oxidation thickness perpendicular to the top and bottom surfaces is fairly uniform in cross-ply laminates for the shorter aging times investigated. However, with increasing aging times, the oxidation front from the top and bottom surfaces tends to become non-uniform, as damage develops, as discussed later.

Figure 4: Oxidation growth near the laminate edge in a *cross-section perpendicular to 0° direction* in $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate as a function of aging time

Figure 5 shows the oxidation growth with aging time in a *cross-section perpendicular to 0° direction* in a $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$ laminate. In this composite lay-up, none of the individual plies (0° , 45° or 90°) have a symmetric distribution of neighboring plies. Hence, the minima or maxima oxidation extent does not occur at the ply mid-planes.

Figure 5: Oxidation growth near the laminate edge in a *cross-section perpendicular to 0° direction* in $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$ laminate as a function of aging time

For example and based on the orientation view of the micrograph in Figure 5, within the 90° layer of the $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$ (*note orientation perpendicular to 0° direction*) laminate, the maximum oxidation extent now occurs closer to the $-45/90$ ply-interface rather than the $90/0$ ply-interface. Similarly, the minimum in the 0° layer of the $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$ laminate occurs closer to the $0/45$ ply-interface, as opposed to the $90/0$ ply-interface. As expected, maximum extent of oxidation occurs in the 90° plies, followed by 45° , -45° and then the 0° ply. For shorter aging times, the oxidation thickness perpendicular to the

top and bottom surfaces is fairly uniform in a quasi-isotropic laminate. However, similar to the observations in a cross-ply laminate, the oxidation front tends to become non-uniform with further increase in aging time, as damage begins to initiate and propagate, as discussed later.

The oxidation growth as a function of aging time near the laminate edges in a $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate is shown in Fig 6. The oxidized region appears as a picture frame near the exposed free surfaces of the specimen for short aging times. However, the front quickly becomes non-uniform in extent with further increase in aging time, similar to the observations in $[0/90]_{4S}$ and $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$ laminates.

Figure 6: Oxidation growth near the laminate edge in $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminate as a function of aging time

The dye-impregnated potted specimens were also viewed under fluorescent light to document the growth and development of damage. Figure 7 compares the fluorescence and dark-field optical microscopy images of $[0]_{16T}$, $[0/90]_{4S}$ and $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$ laminates in a cross-section parallel to the 0° direction in isothermally aged specimens. For each laminate configuration, the fluorescent dye image on the left side of Figure 7 shows short fiber matrix debonds along the 0° fiber direction. Experimental evidence suggests that these debond cracks will continue to increase in length, while new cracks continue to develop at the free surfaces of the specimen with further aging. The right image for each laminate configuration showing the oxidation reveals that the oxidation front is non-uniform, and the oxidation has advanced to a greater extent in the region of the specimen corresponding to the location of the debond cracks. For short aging times, prior to damage development in the axial direction, oxidation growth is fairly uniform along all the exposed edges. However with further aging, axial cracks begin to develop near the edges parallel to the fiber in areas where enhanced oxidation is observed. Thus damage develops as a consequence of oxidation-induced material embrittlement and interfacial and interlaminar stresses induced during curing and resulting from material shrinkage. However, with further increase in aging time, it is these cracks which will then provide pathways for oxygen to diffuse deeper into the specimens and facilitate oxidation deeper into the interior, while new cracks will continue to develop at the exposed free-edges. Therefore, for longer aging times, damage growth is the principal driver for enhanced oxidation growth and the increase in the oxidation axial to thickness anisotropy ratio. Thus, there is a synergistic coupled effect between damage and oxidation development and growth.

Figure 7: Optical microscopy images (fluorescence imaging of cracks and dark-field image of oxidation) in a cross-section parallel to the 0° direction in laminates aged for 1500 hr @ 177°C

SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we will describe the modeling framework required for simulating the oxidation growth in a composite laminate by considering the thermo-oxidative behavior of a single unidirectional ply, and the effect of stacking sequence on the oxidative behavior. The oxidation layer growth in a unidirectional ply is inherently orthotropic due to the presence of the fiber and interphase regions, and is further complicated by the damage growth. In a recent paper [12], we established a framework to differentiate the effects of diffusivity of fiber and fiber-matrix interphase, and those of the discrete damage growth. We treated the fiber and fiber-matrix interphase as a single geometric and material domain and referred to it as the fiber-interphase assemblage. We defined a

scaled diffusivity parameter for the fiber-interphase diffusivity as $D_{ij}^{f*} = D_{ij}^f \frac{C_m^s}{C_f^s}$, where

D_{ij}^f is the fiber-interphase diffusivity and C_m^s and C_f^s are the saturation oxygen concentrations of the matrix and fiber-interphase assemblage, respectively. The solubility and hence the boundary concentration for the matrix is typically known but that for the fiber-interphase assemblage remains largely unknown. Experimental measurements of oxidation layer sizes in undamaged areas of the unidirectional laminate were then utilized to correlate with predictions from the parametric studies with various fiber-interphase diffusivity values. Figure 8 shows the experimentally observed oxidation layer growth in axial (along the fiber) and transverse directions and the simulations matching these observations from the parametric studies. Numerical

results with an assumed orthotropic diffusivity of $D_{11}^{f*} = D_m^{ox}$ and $D_{22}^{f*} = \frac{D_m^{ox}}{10}$ for fiber-

interphase diffusivity correlate well with the experimentally observed values for aging time below 500 hours. After 500 hours, the experimentally observed oxidation layer in the axial direction grows considerably faster and the correlations can only be made with predictions using $D_{11}^{f*} = 10 D_m^{ox}$. This comparison of the experimentally observed and parametrically simulated oxidation growth indicates that either the fiber or the interphase is continuously degrading with aging time. As discrete cracks are often

observed near the fiber-matrix interface during oxidative aging, considerable degradation of the interphase, as indicated by enhanced oxygen diffusivity, is evident from this analysis even in the areas where no discrete cracks can be observed.

Figure 8: Comparison of experimental and simulated results of oxidation layer growth in a unidirectional composite in areas where no damage is observed.

For this analysis, the homogenized properties for the composite lamina (shown with the superscript 'c') are determined using rule of mixtures, and are given in Eq (1) – (4). Eq. (1) defines the homogenized saturation concentration in the composite lamina. As the saturation concentrations are not known at this point, we will assume same solubility for both fiber and matrix. The reaction rate ($R^c(C)$) is homogenized as shown in Eq. (3) and the oxidation state parameter (ϕ_{ox}^c) varies from $\phi_{ox}^c \leq \phi^c \leq 1$. The concentration field, $C(x,y,z;t)$ now represents quantity of dissolved oxygen in the homogenized media and is computed by solving the governing transient diffusion-reaction system.

$$C_c^s = C_m^s V_m + C_f^s V_f \quad (1)$$

$$D_{11}^c = D_{11}^m V_m + D_{11}^f V_f ; \frac{1}{D_{22}^c} = \frac{V_m}{D_{22}^m} + \frac{V_f}{D_{22}^f} \quad (2)$$

$$R^c(C) = V_m R^m(C) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d\phi^c}{dt} = \alpha R^m(C) V_m = \alpha R^c(C) \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_{ox}^c = \phi_{ox}^m + (1 - \phi_{ox}^m) V_f \quad (5)$$

where D_{ij} is the diffusivity tensor, C^s is the saturation oxygen concentration, and the superscript and subscripts m, f and c refer the stated quantities to the matrix, fiber-interphase assemblage and composite, respectively. Using the methodology outlined, we next simulated oxidation growth in a cross-ply laminate. Figure 9 (a) shows the simulated oxidation growth in a cross-section parallel to 0° direction in the $[0/90]_{4s}$ laminate after 100, 150 and 200 hours exposure. The oxidation layer size dependence on the fiber orientation is clearly evident. Figure 9(b) shows three distinct layer sizes depending upon the ply angle as well as the orientation of the neighboring plies. At 200 hours, the smallest oxidation layer size (denoted by length 'A' in the figure) is in the 90°

center ply with a 0° and 90° neighboring ply. The next larger oxidation layer size is in 90° plies that have 0° neighboring plies as denoted by length 'B.' The largest oxidation layer size is for the 0° as denoted by length 'C.' The trends of these numerical simulations are consistent with the experimental results shown earlier in Figure 4.

Figure 9: Oxidation growth in $[0/90]_{4s}$ shown with time and neighbor ply effect.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermo-oxidative degradation of polymer matrix composites is clearly a subject of major importance as designers push the high-temperature endurance limits of polymer composites to improve the performance of aerospace systems. Although the anisotropy in oxidation of unidirectional composites is well documented, limited work has been reported on oxidation of laminated systems. Specifically, little is known about the influence of ply-layup to the transport of oxygen to the interior of the composite.

In this work, the influence of ply stacking sequence on oxidation growth is investigated. Light microscopy techniques are used to characterize the oxidative process in laminated carbon fiber-reinforced polyimide composites. Four different laminates are considered, namely, $[0]_{16T}$, $[0/\pm 45/90]_{2S}$, $[0/90]_{4S}$ and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$. It is shown that the oxidation propagation rate in a ply is strongly influenced by the orientation of its neighboring plies. The observed anisotropy in composite oxidation is explained by carefully monitoring the development and growth of damage in composite specimens through the use of fluorescence imaging using dye impregnation. It is shown that alternative pathways for transport of oxygen into the interior of the composite are fiber-matrix debonds and matrix cracks that propagate with the oxidation front. It has been further determined through closer examination of the oxidation front and the crack front for discrete regions of the specimens, that the oxidation front consistently precedes the crack front. This mechanism for accelerated oxidation is an excellent example of the intrinsic coupling of chemical oxidative aging and damage, which needs to be properly represented in predictive models.

A hierarchical modeling methodology is used to simulate observed oxidation growth patterns in laminated composites. Lamina-scale RVE analyses together with

homogenization techniques are used to determine diffusion, reaction and damage growth parameters to be used at the laminate scale. Oxidation simulations are performed for some selected lamina stacking sequences and the resulting trends are correlated with experimental observations.

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